

Invited Letter

Siemens Digital Industries Works with Education Partners to Offer Hands-On Learning

Keywords: Siemens Digital Industries, automation and digitalization, manufacturing, education-industry partnerships

© 2023 under the terms of the J ATE Open Access Publishing Agreement

Siemens Digital Industries (DI) is an innovation leader in automation and digitalization. Closely collaborating with partners and customers, DI drives digital transformation in the process and discrete industries. With its Digital Enterprise portfolio, DI provides companies of all sizes with an end-to-end set of products, solutions, and services to integrate and digitalize the entire value chain. Optimized for the specific needs of each industry, DI's unique portfolio supports customers to achieve greater productivity and flexibility. In addition, DI is constantly adding innovations to its portfolio to integrate cutting-edge future technologies.

Siemens DI believes the future of manufacturing must be taught in our schools today. To facilitate this, we provide several educational programs that partner with technical colleges to provide hands-on learning and experience on our automation software and hardware. These programs include Siemens Cooperates with Education (SCE), Siemens Mechatronics Systems Certification Program (SMSCP), Lifelong Educational Advantage Program (LEAP), and Siemens Go-PLM.

Participating as an industrial employer with the Preparing Technicians for the Future of Work ATE project team has provided Siemens with the ability to contribute to the tactile execution of educational priorities and influence the strategic direction of industry's collaboration with educational institutions in a positive fashion. The ability to share concepts and practices with others in industry has contributed to changes in our approaches to educational partners and customer conversations.

Of great benefit to educational institutions, the outcomes from these efforts have included understanding skills needs for manufacturing over the next decades. This provides the framework to build a curriculum so that students leave the institution 'work ready' and prepared to face industry challenges today.

Gail Norris
Director, SITRAIN Digital Industries Learning- US
Digital Industries- US
Siemens Industry, Inc.

SIEMENS